

PRINCIPLES FOR TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Annotation. This article discusses the ways to improve the creative cooperation skills of future EFL teachers through the use of "bit-lesson" technology. The analysis of principles of teaching foreign languages are explained.

Keywords: future EFL teacher, technology, creativity, creative cooperation, collaborative pedagogy.

In teaching foreign languages for professional purposes, it is essential:

- the student's personality;
- thinking;
- aesthetic education;
- communicative ability;
- optimal decision-making skills;
- the development of information culture [3].

The technologicalization of the educational process in the teaching of language aspects in foreign languages is organized on the basis of certain methodological, lingvodidactic principles, which focus on teaching communication, a priority in modern foreign language teaching methods - the communicative approach.

In the 80s of the twentieth century, the communicative approach formed in the theory and practice of foreign language teaching began to gain popularity as an effective factor in the organization of student learning activities in an interactive way. According to the leading methodologists I.L.Bim, O.V.Afanaseva, O.A.Radchenko, a communicative approach to teaching communication in foreign languages is a new methodological system that increases the effectiveness of education.

The communicative basis of the technologicalization of foreign language lessons is widely and comprehensively covered in the research of Russian scientists E.I.Passov, S.I.Polat, N.I.Boldyrev, R.P.Milrud and I.R.Maksimova [4.9-10].

Foreign languages accelerate all stages of the educational process. At the same time, based on the use of information technology, it is possible to observe an increase in the quality and efficiency of the educational process, the activation of students' cognitive activity, the deepening of interdisciplinary ties.

The educational purpose of teaching a foreign language in the process of teaching a foreign language is to educate students in the spirit of patriotism, humanity, moral purity, the formation of comprehensively mature, spiritually rich, independent thinkers, honesty, respect for other peoples and their values, faith, friendship, self-esteem, cognition involves cultivating the qualities of willpower. The educational purpose is realized in the process of teaching literary texts in EFL classrooms.

The educational purpose of teaching a foreign language is to develop and improve students' worldview and cognitive skill.[5.5].

At present, foreign language is taught primarily for communicative purposes, and the main task in defining the content of teaching is to teach students to communicate on the most common topics in their daily lives, which stimulates them to speak, think or react. The issue of choosing the topics of speech for the purpose of teaching dialogue is still a matter of debate among methodologists, without finding a final solution.

The formation of skills and competencies is a second component of the content of foreign language teaching. It is known that any activity is automated only if the relevant skills and competencies are formed.

In psychology, the term "ability" is defined as "an automated conscious activity that results from the repetition of a particular mental action many times under the

same conditions." "Qualification" is the ability of a person to apply the acquired knowledge and skills in the process of practical activity.

In order to learn to speak, read and understand a foreign language fluently, it is necessary to develop appropriate skills and abilities. The formation of skills and abilities is a complex psychological process that is in many ways related to cognitive process. Because without cognitive process, no speech can take place. Therefore, in foreign language classes, special attention is paid to the development of students' abstract, logical thinking skills. The more firmly the skills and competencies are formed, the better the students' ability to speak, read and hear, and express their thoughts in writing will develop. The formation of skills and their transformation into abilities is done in the process of doing oral and written exercises.

The third component of the foreign language teaching content is the language material, which is selectively inputted for the special program according to the stages of language teaching. This material includes phonetics, vocabulary, grammar rules, texts and exercises selected according to the educational stages (classes), age, interests of students. Emphasis is placed on the fact that the content of the educational material has primarily universal value and educational, pedagogical, developmental character.

A foreign language teaching program sets the following requirements for the selection of language materials:

1. The use of speech situations that are most often used in students' daily lives to meet their communication needs in the selection of communication topics according to the principle of communicative approach;
2. Formation of certain phonetic, lexical, grammatical and speech skills based on a communicative approach at each stage of education;
3. Focus on mutual exchange of ideas in the formation of speech skills and abilities;

4. Adherence to the phonetic, lexical, grammatical, spelling minimums required in the formation of these skills [6.12].

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